

INTERPRETATION OF INVIOABILITY OF HOME IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES

Fayzyieva Gulrukh Muhammadi kizi

Lecturer of the department

"Constitutional Law"

Tashkent State university of law

Email: tirkashevagulrux999@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0002-2650-0420

The right to inviolability of home occupies an important place in the system of constitutional rights and freedoms of man and citizen. This right is aimed at ensuring the protection of personal space and physical integrity of citizens.

Directly analyzing the constitutional and legal foundations of guaranteeing the inviolability of the home, we studied the constitutions of a number of countries. Based on the scientific and legal analysis carried out, we saw a different approach to the formulation of the right to inviolability of the home and the terminology used in the constitutions of foreign countries. In this connection, we decided to divide the studied constitutions into three main groups, based on the term used to secure the inviolability of the home, namely ¹:

1. Countries where the term inviolability was used of home (*Armenia, Finland, China, Egypt, Greece, Germany, Great Britain, Brazil, Belgium, Estonia, etc.*);

2. Countries where the term inviolability was used of residence / domicile / dwelling (*Azerbaijan, Albania, Argentina, Moldova, Central African Republic, Czech Republic, etc.*);

¹ This information is relevant at the time of writing this dissertation.

3. Countries where the right to inviolability of the home is tied directly to the concepts of privacy or property in the constitutions (*Belarus* , *United Arab Emirates*, *Japan*, *France*, *India*, *etc.*).

Directly discussing the constitutions of foreign countries, we saw the use of different terminologies to express the concept of home, which is clearly related to the correct interpretation where the term inviolability of home , inviolability of residence, inviolability of domicile, inviolability of dwelling is used . We will try to interpret these concepts by studying the constitutions of such countries as: Armenia, Finland, China, Egypt, Greece, Germany, Great Britain, Brazil, Belgium, Estonia, Azerbaijan, Albania, Argentina, Moldova, Central African Republic, Czech Republic .

At first glance, the above terms denote the inviolability of the home, but if you pay attention to the expressions for designating a home, they differ from each other (home, residence, dwelling, domicile). In this connection, we need to analyze and study their similarities and differences in the application and interpretation of constitutional norms of foreign countries.

Home is the physical place where a person usually lives or feels at home. It may also include an emotional aspect, with feelings of belonging, comfort and safety.

Residence is any place that indicates the place where a person resides. It can also cover both permanent and temporary residence, and can be used in a variety of contexts such as rentals, tourism, etc.

Dwelling is any place intended for habitation, which includes various types of dwellings, such as houses, apartments, cottages, apartments and other forms of dwellings.

Domicile - registration at the place of residence, associated with the legal status of the place of residence (for example, to determine tax status, or other legal obligations).

Analyzing each of these terms, we can say that the concepts of residence and dwelling are synonymous, and are more identified with the concept of place of residence. Whereas the term home, puts more emphasis on a specific building that meets certain requirements (for example: sanitary, technical, etc.), on the one hand. On the other hand, it focuses on the psychological state of a person, namely on feelings of belonging, comfort and security. And another term is domicile, which means registration at the place of residence, in order to ensure the fulfillment of certain obligations or determine the legal status of a person (for example: tax status, during elections, voter, etc.).

To summarize, we can say that each of these terms pays attention to different characteristics of the place of residence, which emphasizes the diversity and versatility of the concept of “home” in social, emotional and legal terms. The differences between these terms can be subtle and depend on context and source. However, in general, they all embody the right to the inviolability of the home, with varying emphasis on details such as formal status or specific characteristics of the home.

When conducting a comparative analysis of the constitutions of different countries and dividing them into three groups, the researcher took into account the peculiarities of using the above terms. Based on the term used, we can see from what angle the emphasis was placed on the concept of inviolability of the home, including the concept of home itself.

